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**EVALUATING SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DISPOSAL METHODS:
A CASE STUDY OF ILESHA GARAGE MOTOR SPARE PARTS MARKETS
AKURE.**

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the current sustainable solid waste and its method of disposal in the Ilesha garage motor spare parts market in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria, with the intention of suggesting tactics that will enhance effective solid waste management methods and culture. This study utilized a combination of quantitative research methods (case studies) and stakeholder interviews, with waste management authorities and company shop owners. Findings revealed that their major primary way of disposing solid garbage is open dumping, where unused motor spare parts are dumped at parking lots unkempt, resulting in environmental pollution and public health issues. This presents a major challenge to the state organization charge of solid waste management that are already burdened with insufficient funding, lack of equipment, training, and skilled workers, as well as the carefree attitude of waste producers and spare parts vendors toward solid waste management in Ilesha Garage, Akure. This study therefore suggested improving solid waste management (SWM) strategies, emphasizing recycling and reuse, and fostering collaborative training among motor spare part vendors.

KEYWORDS: *Sustainability, Environment, Solid Waste Management, Disposal, Ilesha Garage Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent time, when the issue of waste management is discussed, it is important to answer the question, what exactly is waste? (Ahmed et al., 2023). Continual global energy scarcity and its future challenges, as well as environmental disasters, are causing global devastation. Waheeg et al., (2023). described waste as a useless byproduct of human activities that physically contains the same substance that is available in the useful product. It has also been defined as any product or material that is useless to the producer. This means that the term "waste" is subjective. What is a waste to one person could be a useful material or resource to another. Waste can be categorized into solid, liquid, and gaseous waste. Examples of solid waste are municipal solid waste, industrial solid waste, agricultural solid waste, construction and demolition waste, etc. Liquid wastes are the sewage, industrial wastewater, agricultural wastewater, etc. Gaseous wastes are the industrial emissions, vehicle emissions, combustion gases, etc. It is also categorized by its source, which is domestic, industrial, commercial, agricultural, medical, construction, and demolition waste, etc.

Waste can also be categorized by biodegradability. Biodegradable waste can be broken down naturally, while non-biodegradable waste cannot be naturally broken down according to Dehghani et al., (2021). Solid waste, as described by the State of Vermont Agency of Natural Resources Department of Environmental Conservation (2012), is any tangible and non-free-flowing unwanted material or substance that results from human activities as reported by Obunwo et al., (2023). While Khan et al., (2022) referred to them as municipal solid waste where its sources are generated from commercial, agricultural, and industrial operations Waste management in Nigeria is a big issue. Collection and management in the proper way in the country is only about 20-30%, according to the Consul General of Switzerland in Lagos (2023). This results in some parts of Nigeria not being habitable; malaria and other deadly diseases are given enough room to thrive.

In Ondo State, the situation is similar, as pointed out by Olorunlana et al. (2022). In Akure, waste is generated faster than it is collected, transported, and disposed. Also, the management of the wastes is not satisfactory. One of the major places that generate lots of waste in Akure is the Ilesha Garage Motor spare parts. The place generates lots of waste because it houses lots of activities, which include mechanic workshops and buying and selling car parts, among other activities. Also, no visible waste management mechanisms, such as waste bins, can be seen on site.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

According to Onuegbu *et al.*, (2024), solid waste management is the application of techniques that ensures the orderly execution of the functions of collecting, transfer, processing, treatment and disposal of solid waste. Various methods of waste management techniques have been adopted in various cities in Nigeria which has not been able to provide the best solution hence the need for Sustainable Waste management methods. Abubakar *et al.*, (2022), described sustainable waste management as methods designed to help provide solutions which will not have adverse effect on human health and the environment. Lange, (2021) indicated that the process of achieving this involves collecting the waste, sorting and processing them, recovering of materials or energy from the waste and recycling them into new products. Therefore, when we begin to think in this line and the various ways of waste management methods which include recycling, reuse, smart waste collection, recovering energy from waste etc., we can begin to imagine waste management practices as not burdensome after all and waste as a potential raw material. Waste which could be solid, liquid or gas can be converted into new and useful products. This is important in achieving sustainability in waste management which will reduce the negative impact on our environment and help conserve resources. Reducing pollution and helping to yield substantial economic and social benefits. (Hasmori *et al.*, 2020). To bridge these gaps, there should be sustainable waste streams and ensuring good practices to reduce the rates of generated solid waste.

- **Aim**

The aim of this study is to study how solid waste are managed and disposed at Ilesha garage Akure.

- **Objectives**

The objectives of this study therefore include to;

1. Identify solid waste hierarchy, category and integrating it into waste management component that will handle Solid waste generated at Ilesha garage.
2. Establish comprehensive system for collection, transportation and disposal of waste in relation to waste management regulations that adhere to state waste management specifications.

METHODOLOGY

- **Study Area**

The presence of several homes, businesses, cars, etc., gives the neighbourhood a cosmopolitan appeal. This draws in people for work and business from all over Ondo State. Latitudes 110 10` and 110 11` North and longitudes 07 0 37 ` and 7 0 40} South are roughly where it is located. Residents, however, dispose of their rubbish in open areas because the area lacks infrastructure for government-approved waste disposal. Olaleye (2023). Poor trash management in Ilesha Garage Motor Park is a result of the majority of these ignorant individuals being indifferent to the environment and its aesthetics.

Figure 1: showing the location map of Ilesha garage motor spare parts

Source: Researchers field survey, 2025.

Figure 1 showing the site location map of Ilesha garage showing shops, waste dumped and road networks, shops, road networks and adjoining buildings.

METHODOLOGY

The methods used for this research is a combined/mixed method of interview, direct observation of the waste types and storage/disposal habits in Ilesha garage motor spare parts, interviewing some key (case studies) stakeholders, including shop owners and waste management authorities in Ilesha garage Akure. However, in the research design, a survey questionnaire was adopted to evaluate the interest of motor spare part sellers using percentage, levels, frequencies to evaluate their knowledge and response level. A total of Seventy-three Questionnaires were administered, Six-two were recovered while Eleven Questionnaire were missing.

RESULTS

Findings from the study are presented in tables as indicated below;

Table 1: Showing Motor spare parts sellers cadre and years of experience of respondents in Percentages.

Sellers Cadre	Number of responses	Percentage of responses	Years of experience	Number of responses	Percentage of responses
Manager	21	33.87	0-9	16	25.80
Senior	10	16.13	10-19	32	51.61
Junior	13	20.97	20-24	9	14.53
Others	18	29.03	25&Above	5	8.06
Total	62	100%	Total	62	100%

Table 1 shows the number of spare parts cadre and their years of experiences. The results from the table revealed that 33.87% of responses were in the highest managing role of the sellers in Ilesha garage and their percentage years of experience is 51.61%.

Table 2: Showing Tribes and age range of respondents in Percentages

Tribe(s)	Number of responses	Percentage of responses	Age range	Number of responses	Percentage of responses
Hausa	6	9.68	0-15years	3	4.85
Igbo	26	41.94	16-29years	23	37.09
Yoruba	18	29.03	30-49years	21	33.87
Others	12	19.35	50&Above	15	24.19
Total	62	100%	Total	62	100%

Table 2 results revealing Igbo tribe 41.94% having the highest number percentile constituting solid waste in the area with the age range of 30-49years (33.87%). While, Hausa, Yoruba and other revealed 9.68%, 29.03%, 19.35% with their different Age range percentage involved.

Table 3: Showing Waste disposal methods and type of solid waste generated in Ilesha garage motor spare parts Akure.

Waste disposal methods	Number of responses	Percentage of responses	Types of Solid Waste	Number of responses	Percentage of responses
Incinerator	09	14.52	Glass	07	11.29
Ocean Dumping	02	3.23	Aluminums	11	17.74
Open Dumped site	30	48.39	Iron	13	24.19
Landfilling	08	12.90	Rubber	06	9.68
Recycling	05	8.06	Plastics	02	3.22
Others	08	12.90	Nylon	05	8.06
			Papers	03	4.84
			Others	15	20.98
Total	62	100%	Total	62	100%

Table 3 presents methods of waste disposal and the type of solid waste generated. This indicates that open dumped site (48.39%) constitutes their major methods of waste disposal likewise Iron (24.19%) also constitutes the major type of solid waste generated in the area due the highest number of percentage results.

Table 4: Showing the sources of solid waste and causes in Ilesha garage motor spare parts.

Sources of solid waste	Number of responses	Percentage of responses	Causes of the solid waste	Number of responses	Percentage of responses
Vandalism	17	27.42	Inadequate security	10	16.13
Residual such as off-cuts	22	35.49	cutting materials to length and packaging	16	25.81
Damaged vehicle	15	24.19	Accidents/Outdated Vehicle	23	37.09
Others	08	12.90	Lack of waste management Plan	13	20.97
Total	62	100%	Total	62	100%

Table 4 indicates the source of solid waste and causes of the solid waste in Ilesha garage motor spare parts Akure, Residual such as off-cuts constitutes 35.49% which dominates more sources than others while accidents/Outdated Vehicles 37.09% constitutes major causes of the solid waste.

The above figure summarizes the overall results presented in Tables 1 through 4. Table 1 shows that managers constitute the highest proportion of spare parts sellers, accounting for 33.87%, and they also represent those with the most years of experience in the business. Table 2 indicates that the Igbo tribe is the most represented group among spare parts sellers, comprising 41.94% of the respondents within the study area. Furthermore, open dumping (48.39%) is identified as the most common method of waste disposal, while offcuts (35.49%) represent the predominant source of solid waste generated.

Figure 3: showing several methods and their percentage activities used in achieving sustainable motor spare parts in Ilesha garage, Akure Axis.

The figure above reveals several methods and activities in achieving sustainable solid waste management in the motor spare parts garage carried out during the survey. Waste collection constitutes 16%, waste disposal 53%, Resellers of spare parts 10% while the recycling constitutes 7%, this is to showcase that the methods of waste disposal is open dumped site which is more dominate and peculiar as their activities in such area. The recycling of these waste is too infinitesimal and the resellers prefer to resell majority of the spare parts to people and dumped the damages ones in an open dumped site around the place.

- **Disposal of Solid waste management at present**

At present all the waste gathered and collected from Ilesha garage motor spare part Akure are disposed in open dump yards without proper processing for recycling. However, some useful spare parts from vehicles generated as solid waste are kept in the seller's shop for them to resell to people either in large quantity or small quantity.

DISCUSSION

From the results, we analyzed the data to showcase our key findings, followed by detailed explanations as shown with Number of responses and percentage of responses. These results indicate that, majority of the motor spare parts sellers holds managerial positions. i.e they dominate the market and possess extensive experience than others in selling motor spare parts however, Igbo tribe have the highest number percentile constituting solid waste in the area with the age range of 30-49years. This gives the relationship, similarities and methods of waste disposal and the type of waste been generated, however, this revealed that Open dumped site (48.39%) constitutes highest methods of waste disposal in Ilesha garage motor spare parts with the type of waste Iron (24.19%) constitutes more of the type of solid waste in the environment compare to other causes. In the same vein, the results also revealed that majority of the sources of the solid waste were from the residual of vehicles such as off-cuts (35.49%) and majority causes of these solid waste are from accidents/Outdated vehicles (37.09%) which is paramount to the area. However, this study shows that inadequately managed solid waste has a detrimental impact on people's health. This pattern matches findings by Nnenna et al. (2025) in a market in southeast Nigeria, where car-related markets had similar types of waste, mostly made up of non-biodegradable materials, showing that the type of business affects the kind of waste produced.

CONCLUSION

After carefully studying how solid waste are managed at Ilesha Garage, this study concluded that solid waste is not being properly managed at Ilesha garage. The final course of action on waste disposal at the research indicates is open Dumpsite which is harmful to the society and can lead to an outbreak of diseases. Protecting the Environment is a very important job that is meant for all; hence the government should look into integrated waste management in order to properly manage the waste being generated at Ilesha garage. However, the government should support efficient waste management by doing the following; Sensitizing the general public on the needs and benefits of disposing off of their wastes through appropriate channels and methods of disposal. Provide adequate waste management infrastructures and Manpower Allocating more funds to developing of modern waste management Infrastructures.

- **Recommendations**

In light of the study's conclusions, we recommended the following actions to help Ilesha Garage Motor Spare Part Akure achieve adequate solid waste management:

- i. The public should be made aware of the significance of properly disposing of garbage.
- ii. The government, companies, residents, and all other stakeholders should be included in the process.
- iii. The state government should vigorously enforce the bylaws governing the disposal of waste.
- iv. As a way to motivate the populace, the state government needs to provide incentives for recycling and waste minimization.
- v. For the best waste disposal, the government should support public-private partnerships.

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